

Variety	Original line	Year of release	Duration (days)	Reaction ^a to BPH biotype 2	Agronomic traits
NN3A	IR2071-625-1-252 (IR36)	1977	110	R	Moderate lodging, dwarf stature
NN5A	IR2071-179-3	1977	115	MR	High percentage of unfilled grains
NN6A	IR2307-247-2-2-3	1979	115	R	Hard straw, more high yielding than NN3A
NN2B	IR2823-399-5-6	1979	125	R	Tolerance for blast, acid sulfate soils; semi-dwarf stature
NN3B	IR2797-115-3	1979	125	R	Tolerance for acid sulfate soils; semidwarf stature
MTL30	IR9129-192-2-3-5	1980	100	R	Very short duration for rotation with soy-bean

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

program for BPH. Additional control components utilized are the herding of baby ducks, raising of fish, and mass-

installation of light traps. To protect the resistant varieties from reinfestation by new biotypes, government authorities

prohibit the planting of susceptible varieties in the high-yielding rice areas. ■

Varietal reaction to rice stem borer under different nitrogen levels

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Four prerelease varieties — CRM 10-5747, AD9408, AS 1374, and PL 29 and standard TKM9—were evaluated for their reaction to rice stem borer under 5 levels of nitrogen — 0, 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg/ha at the Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur, during 1979–80 navarai (December–January to April–May). The trial, comprising two replications, used the split-plot design with varieties as main treatments and nitrogen levels as subtreatments.

Assessment of stem borer infestation was based on deadheart incidence at 60 days after transplanting and whitehead occurrence at harvest. The infestation percentages were determined and the data were analyzed statistically.

The results obtained for variety and N level were statistically significant. AD9408 and CRM 10-5747, were least infested (see table). The other three varieties had significantly higher infestation. Nitrogen level and stem borer incidence were positively correlated. Pest infestation increased with nitrogen level. The no-nitrogen treatment had the least incidence while the treatment with 40 kg N/ha had moderate infestation. Infestation was high with higher N levels; it was highest with 160 kg N/ha. ■

Varietal reaction to rice stem borer under different N levels, 1979–80 navarai.

N level (kg/ha)	Deadheart and whitehead incidence (%)					Mean infestation % (angles)	CD
	TKM9	CRM 10-5747	AD 9408	AS 1374	PL 29		
0	12.08	9.06	9.06	12.23	14.76	11.44	
40	13.44	12.28	9.84	17.44	16.34	13.87	
80	24.55	10.53	10.76	17.45	22.97	17.25	2.38
120	23.95	12.92	11.54	21.96	24.34	18.94	
160	26.90	15.46	11.16	22.69	23.90	20.02	
Mean infestation % (angles)	20.18	12.04	10.47	18.35	20.46		
CD for main treatment	4.54						
CD for interaction	N.S.						
conclusion:							
Varieties	AD 9408	CRM 10-5747	AS 1374	TKM9	PL 29		
N levels	0	40	80	120	160		

Screening rice varieties and breeding lines for thrip resistance in late bora

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The rice thrip is now considered a major pest on the late-planted boro rice crop at the BRRI farm, Joydebpur. The main symptoms are leaf rolling from the tip and drying leaf tips. In severe infestations, the plants are stunted and the lower leaves die.

In the field, 390 entries from IRRI were screened for resistance to thrips. Thirty-day-old seedlings were planted on 22 February 1979. Each line was planted in 2 rows in a 5.4-m – long plot, spaced

25 × 15 cm, with 1 seedling/hill.

Fertilizer was applied at 100-80-80 kg NPK/ha. The basal dose was 50-80-60 kg NPK/ha and the rest of the nitrogen was topdressed in 2 equal splits. No protective measures were taken. Scoring at 25 days after planting used this scale:

Thrips grading scale

R	1 = light infestation (just leaf tip rolling)
MR	3 = medium light infestation (20–30% leaf rolling)
MS	5 = medium infestation (30–50% leaf rolling)
S	7 = medium heavy infestation (50–75% leaf rolling)
HS	9 = heavy infestation (75–100% leaf rolling)